

TECHNOLOGICAL BASIS OF DEVELOPING THE KNOWLEDGE OF FUTURE PHYSICAL EDUCATION TEACHERS ABOUT SPORTS TOURISM

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Annotation: This article describes the peculiarities of training future physical education teachers for sports tourism, opinions on the development of various reforms in society.

Key words and phrases: socio-economic, independent education, modern outlook, social necessity, continuous education, physical education teachers, innovative and digital, educational standards, Education and training, scientific-methodical.

Introduction

In modern conditions, one of the necessary conditions for increasing the effectiveness of developing the knowledge of future physical education teachers about sports tourism is to organize this process on a technological basis. In educational practice, educational, pedagogic, training, teaching technologies are distinguished. There are a number of reasons that increase the need to develop the knowledge of future physical education teachers about sports tourism. This is an exciting and complex process that directly increases the effectiveness of physical education and training.

Materials and Methods

Classification signs of pedagogical technology aimed at developing the knowledge of future physical education teachers about sports tourism were determined as follows: level of application and description: mesotechnology with a description of application at the local level; philosophical basis: 1) anthropological; 2) ontological; 3) dialogic; methodological approach: humane, algorithmic, practical, value-oriented approach; leading factors of development: 1) sociogenic; 2) psychogenic; scientific concept of mastering experience: associative-reflexive + active + developmental + behavioristic; according to the content: for higher physical education courses; type of socio-pedagogical activity: educational (didactic), physical, mental, developmental; used methods: 1) dialogic; 2) situational; 3) explaining to each other; 4) teach each other; 3) independent work; 4) game; 5) investigative-research; organizational forms: 1) individual; 2) group; 3) work in pairs; 4) collective; used tools: 1) resources; 2) physical exercises; 3) physical, mental and will education; 4) motivational

education; approach to the student and description of educational interaction: person-oriented; modernization direction and attitude to the traditional education system: pedagogical technology based on strengthening the physical-educational function; category of use: for students of higher education institutions.

When educational tourism is launched, it is possible to go to self-learning language courses, restaurants, places of rest for students outside of studies, cultural recreation (going to museums, theaters, movies, concerts).) will increase in demand and need.

Therefore, the tourism culture is understood as the acquisition of knowledge related to the further development of personnel exchange, conducting projects in cooperation with international universities, holding international conferences, participating in sports competitions. The development of educational tourism in Uzbekistan will be a great impetus to the country's economic growth and will allow it to stand among developed countries. A fast modern system of information exchange with foreign countries will be formed, social and economic relations will be strengthened, and most importantly, the level of knowledge and spirituality of people will increase and unite peoples.[1]

Voluntary tourism is one of the most developing types of tourism among young people.

Cultural exchange. This tour includes not only students, but also young artists, sportsmen, and cultural workers, identifying similarities and differences between peoples, nationalities, getting to know each other, and exchanging ideas.

In sports and adventure tourism, young people travel to participate in and watch international sports competitions, participate in adventure tourism, and have active recreation.

For recreation, young people travel in peace and quiet, mainly to be in nature, to do their favorite activities and to discover new things for themselves. Year by year, the number of young people traveling internationally is increasing, and their spending in the countries they visit is also increasing. According to statistics, youth tourism accounted for 15% of the total tourism market in 1991, 23% in 1995, 20% in 2000, 24% in 2005, and 300 million people in 2020.[2:42]

Results

Based on the above, it can be said that each type of youth tourism has its own characteristics and plays an important role in the implementation of trips of young people as owners of tourism culture.

Another important factor in the development of tourism culture in our country is high-quality education and training of specialists in tourism. Organization of the educational process in the field of tourism is currently one of the rapidly developing directions. Humanities, social, geographical, economic and other sciences are embodied in it, so it belongs to the scope of multifaceted sciences. The introduction of a flexible and diverse education system is a major impetus for education in the field of tourism. The demand for a specialist in the field of tourism, who faces great competition in the labor market, is growing. The modern model of a tourism specialist includes the following: psychological components, possession of interdisciplinary knowledge in tourism areas, the ability to apply them in practice, professional knowledge and skills, skills in modern computer technologies. , knowing several foreign languages. For this reason, it is not enough to have a general understanding of each area, the demand for creating a perspective branch education system is increasing. Because modern specialists need interdisciplinary knowledge and professional skills related to the standard of education.

Observing positive changes in the field of tourism has led to an increase in the demand for these specialists in Uzbekistan, and the training of specialists must lead to an increase in the demand for this sector. Such a situation has led to the creation of educational universities, colleges, lyceums in various directions related to tourism, the purpose of which is to train personnel in educational courses and specialties.

The field of tourist services includes the complex tourist infrastructure that affects the development of tourist business and the quality of tourist services in the region. It determines the interaction of the "Additional tourist services" network with other sectors of the economy (the sphere of material production and services).

Despite the influence of other sectors, the effectiveness of tourism depends on the provision of organizational and economic conditions, which can be achieved on the basis of solving the issues of state policy in managing the regional tourism sector.

Based on the approach of developing tourism culture in Uzbekistan, formation of tourist awareness among citizens and socio-political and cultural views that have a positive effect on the development of the industry, a survey was conducted in selected regions of Fergana region, involving 970 respondents. The results of the survey were formed on the basis of the following tourist directions

and goals, taking into account the supply and demand of tourists (domestic and foreign) visiting the regions of our country.

The decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on February 7, 2018 "On measures to ensure the rapid development of domestic tourism" [3] further increased the possibility of using existing tourism resources in our country and provides support for the development of tourism on the basis of private partnerships holds Another unique feature of this decision is that now, based on the mentioned decision, every business entity has the opportunity to send its employees on tourist trips without difficulty, and ultimately, it has a convenient opportunity that serves to increase labor productivity. The decision should serve to prevent unnecessary harassment of the company's management by state inspection bodies in the future. In a word, it was possible to get rid of corruption due to the legal solution of the social problem.

A factor that directly affects the attraction of tourists is the provision of qualified personnel in the field. Therefore, the decree mentions the need to improve personnel training, retraining, qualification, and post-higher education. Also, acceleration of the airport service, which is of great importance for the development of tourism, is one of the main issues of the decree.

In the framework of cultural exchange, attention is focused on the activation of the transport logistics service that serves tourists in accordance with the demand of the time and the consistent improvement of its quality.

An important prospective direction of the development of Uzbek tourism is, first of all, the training of qualified personnel who will serve in this field in the future and actively promote the tourism culture of our people through them. Therefore, in recent years, a number of practical steps have been taken in this regard. On the basis of the Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 3815 of June 28, 2018, the "Silk Road" International Tourism University was established in the city of Samarkand. In the 2019-2020 academic year, the university opened a number of courses for students, such as pilgrimage tourism, ecotourism, digital tourism, hotel tourism, event management, international relations in the field of tourism, and law. [5] The most important issue that needs to be resolved is the formation of qualified specialist personnel who will conduct training in such newly opened directions.

"Attracting investments to the field of tourism, raising the potential of future personnel, we need to take constructive measures to increase the culture of tourism in them," says the President of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev, "Our culture of tourism is often our ancient cities, historical and cultural monuments."

is limited within. Today, the unique nature of our republic, nature reserves, mountainous regions are of great importance for the further development of tourism.

The development of recreational tourism, pilgrimage and ecological tourism in our country gives a great impetus to the development of economic development and social spheres".

One of the most important foundations for the development of tourism culture in our country is educational foundations. Especially in this regard, it is time to take important steps in the development of tourism culture based on the training of modern personnel for the ecotourism direction of the tourism sector. There are many favorable areas for the formation of ecotourism in the territory of our republic. For example, taking into account the geographical location and historical past of the Samarkand region, the following settlements can be included in the ecoregions to be established: settlements in the city of Urgut, where thousand-year-old maple trees grow, miraculous holes located on the road to Amonqo'ton, the geographical location of this settlement and its areas rich in environmentally friendly fruits are among them.

The colorful courtyards planted with flowers, the rural life rich in Uzbek traditions of our nation will serve as an important factor for the establishment of modern ecotourism, and it will be possible to turn into attractive places of interest. In general, for the development of eco-tourism and agro-tourism, there are a lot of geographical areas in the republic, it is necessary to identify them, train and increase the number of specialists who are geographically knowledgeable, who understand ecological education and culture. There are specialists in various fields in our country, but the number of specialists in the field of tourism and ecology is limited, the reason for this is the lack of demand for specialists in this field.[7]

It can be said that there are some obstacles in the development of eco- and agro-tourism, because the population and the guides lack experience in this field. "Silk Road" International Tourism University, Paris Academy of France, Sahid Tourism Institute (Indonesia), Sochi State University, etc.

Tourism is the main source of income for the state budget in many countries of the world. It may be promising to organize scientifically based routes of ecotourism in historical monuments, monuments, springs, maples, inscriptions on stones, nature reserves, "Jayron" eco-center, national parks.

Today, for the first time, the creation of the "Road map" for the formation of eco- and agro-tourism is being implemented in our republic. At the beginning of this

work, specialists from various fields have started work, but the first task remains the issue of personnel. In higher education institutions, it is necessary to include enough hours of ecology and geography lessons in the curriculum, to educate young specialists in ecological culture and in-depth geographical knowledge. Using new technologies to form ecotourism and bring it to the level of "clustering" will give positive results.

The main goal of the adoption of the Law "On Education" and the "National Program of Personnel Training" and the "Concept of Development of the Higher Education System until 2030" is the democratic changes and market reforms of the personnel training system. non-compliance with the requirements, inability of the current educational system to meet the requirements of today, insufficient material-technical and information base of the educational process, lack of quality educational-methodical and scientific literature and didactic materials, educational system, lack of mutual cooperation and mutually beneficial integration between science and production, teachers' lack of modern knowledge, skills and qualifications that enable them to provide students with modern knowledge, lack of highly qualified pedagogic personnel, personnel It is explained by the fact that it is aimed at eliminating serious deficiencies in the existing system of training.

[8:101] The main role in eliminating the above-mentioned shortcomings is played by the teacher. Therefore, the successful solution of these problems depends on the professional and pedagogical training of future teachers.[9:6]

In this regard, it is appropriate to teach "Tourism ethics and culture" to undergraduate students. The main task of this subject is to reveal the complex relationship between society and nature, to create knowledge, skills and abilities in tourism and ecotourism in students, and it should be focused on solving the following tasks. In particular:

- by developing the theoretical foundations of students' knowledge, skills and abilities in tourism, ecotourism, tourism ethics, travel etiquette, justifying the actual pedagogical importance of the problem;
- to sufficiently inculcate the formation of knowledge, qualifications and skills in tourism, ecotourism, tourism ethics, travel etiquette into the current curriculum, programs and textbooks;
- development of technologies for pedagogical assessment of the essence of the methods and approaches used in the process of formation of knowledge, skills and skills in tourism, ecotourism, tourism ethics, travel etiquette and the principles of its selection;

- on the basis of modern pedagogical technologies, to determine the interactive methods of creating knowledge, skills and skills in tourism, ecotourism, tourism ethics, travel etiquette in students, to develop the methodology of their implementation and to apply them to the educational process in a timely manner;- development of practical-methodical recommendations on the formation of knowledge, skills and skills in tourism, ecotourism, tourism ethics, travel etiquette in students;
- to inculcate in students the ideas of patriotism, love for nature and respect for it by creating knowledge, skills and abilities in tourism, ecotourism, tourism ethics, travel etiquette;
- the successful solution of the problems of tourism, ecotourism, tourism ethics, travel etiquette in students, regardless of the field occupied by future young professionals, will help to create the existence, the civilization created by the peoples and states in it, owned and allows to form sufficient ideas about the nature that is obliged to protect.

For this purpose, in order to organize the educational process and increase the knowledge, skills and abilities of future specialists in tourism, ecotourism, tourism ethics, travel etiquette, and to eliminate the noted problems in their professional training:

- taking into account the state and social orders, conducting research on the formation of knowledge, skills and skills of future specialists in tourism, ecotourism, tourism ethics, travel etiquette, modernizing educational paradigms and developing solutions to conceptual problems;
- formation of clear visions of future specialists in the formation of knowledge, skills and skills in tourism, ecotourism, tourism ethics, travel etiquette;
- acquisition of special requirements and necessary professional knowledge, qualifications and skills that allow organizing professional activity based on the requirements of society and social development;
- mastering the formation of knowledge, qualifications and skills related to the special level of professional training - tourism, ecotourism, tourism ethics, travel etiquette;
- to decide on an innovative approach that is the basis for the development and improvement of knowledge, skills and skills of future specialists in tourism, ecotourism, tourism ethics, travel etiquette.

This process, in turn, increases the social prestige of tourism culture and serves to create a national model of personnel training. The successful solution of these tasks, in turn, is an important factor in the formation of knowledge, skills and

abilities of future specialists in tourism, ecotourism, tourism ethics, travel etiquette.

The development of solutions to the mentioned problems and the successful solution of these tasks directly depends on the level of professional and pedagogical formation of future specialists in tourism, ecotourism, tourism ethics, and travel etiquette. Also, in our country, "organization of qualification assessment of personnel and graduates of vocational education institutions in the field of tourism; creation of a continuous, multi-level education system that meets international requirements in the field of tourism, employees of the tourism industry who provide direct tourist services in the field of domestic and inbound tourism (guides, guide-observers, subjects of tourism activities, catering organizations, transport, etc. employees) development of standards that determine mandatory qualification requirements, development and implementation of a system for training tourism employees in the rules of providing information to tourists and safety instructions, education to improve the system of personnel training in the tourism sector by involving foreign specialists in the process, as well as to organize the system of personnel training in the tourism sector, including increasing the number of educational institutions in the regions, opening branches of leading foreign higher educational institutions for training personnel in the tourism sector" It is not for nothing that such things have been determined.[9]

As a result of the rapid spread of the information flow, the integration of nations and cultures, as well as the rapid adaptation of the student to the "informational environment", the fundamental revision of the principles and methods of education has become an urgent issue all over the world. Today's student personality or calling the youth to education is reaching the level of "art". In recent years, various new ideas and concepts have entered our national pedagogy. In particular, the use of the innovative cluster of pedagogical education is becoming popular. In fact, although the concept of "cluster" is terminologically new in the field, it is essentially not foreign to Eastern pedagogy. That is, the cooperation of institutions and means aimed at one goal, in other words, reaching the intended destination in a united way. During the study of this issue, it was determined that it would be indirectly effective. This is the development of educational tourism, be it or not.[10:45]

More precisely, innovative processes are actively developing pedagogical theory and practice, and educational tourism is one of these tools. All methods and forms of modern teaching can be effectively used in this. Forms and technologies

of education that have been actively practiced until now have a fundamental basis. But educational tourism is also needed to actively educate the "virtual world people" who are wirelessly connected to multimedia tools.

When studying the pedagogy and education policy of foreign countries, it can be observed that special importance is attached to this area. For example, educational tourism is actively used in Russia and Europe. It is widely used in various educational systems and is evaluated by innovative pedagogues as a highly effective teaching technology. Educational tourism refers to the plans and tasks defined in the curricula of secondary, secondary special and higher educational institutions. types of excursions organized for the purpose of performance are understood.

If we assume that the innovative cluster of pedagogical education covers the subjects of lower, secondary and higher educational institutions, educational tourism is also extracurricular and secondary, as well as university, post-graduate, in order to achieve a certain goal. , combines types of education outside the university.

The goal of educational tourism is also the opportunity to satisfy the interest in conceptual-scientific, practical and professional development and learning. The Chirchik State Pedagogical Institute of the Tashkent region has started using the Pedagogical Education Innovation Cluster method in order to develop the field of education in the region. In the use of this method, it is possible to add educational tourism, which contributes to the development of the educational system in the region. For this, it is one of the higher educational institutions in the region with a favorable geographical environment and scientific potential.

As a result of socio-political and cultural reforms carried out in our republic in recent years, as a result of holding international conferences, festivals, international scientific and practical conferences, the interest of tourists and participants of various ages in our country is increasing more and more. For the development of educational tourism, it is appropriate for educational institutions to conclude cooperation agreements with tour agencies and companies. For example, a student or a group of students can work as a volunteer for a particular tourism company. As a result of guiding a small group of tourists, the student will further strengthen the history, cultural heritage and language skills of our country. This is the goal of educational tourism in itself.

In the educational policy of Uzbekistan, it is of strategic importance to focus on the development of educational tourism, that is, it is necessary to develop the basis of educational tourism on the basis of educational trips and excursions of

secondary school students and university students. For example, based on the direction of a specific higher education institution, it is appropriate to develop rules and criteria for programs aimed at teaching language, information technology, the field of art, archeology, and history. It will be more useful if the program plans are carried out mainly between the winter and summer holidays.

Discussion

Educational tourism is one of the types of tourism that combines cultural and educational activities with knowledge, making good use of free time. If the practical learning of all subjects is the primary goal, the means to achieve it can be the secondary goal of this vacation. Educational tourism can vary depending on the reason and topic of the trip. If the excursion includes education with elements of recreation, language courses, study at foreign educational institutions, visits to exhibitions and museums, tours to historical sites, production enterprises, seminars and conferences are of purely scientific and practical importance. have

The characteristics, organization and conduct of the educational tourism program are determined by a number of factors. The main thing is that the educational purpose of the trips should be carefully developed based on the peculiarities of the region, the duration of the trip, the season, the age, experience, and training of the tour participants, the possibility of financial expenses for the tourist group and the educational group, and others.

Based on the natural, cultural, historical, handicraft resources of the area visited on the basis of educational tourism, it is important to determine the prospects for the development of specialized types of educational tourism here. Such sources of tourism have a number of unique features. The informational, ecological, social, aesthetic, cultural or other value of each resource, as well as their combinations, are of particular importance in the assessment of educational tourism and the resource potential of the region. Important parameters of educational tourism resources, of course, include such characteristics as capacity, stability, reliability and availability.

Cities rich in historical monuments such as Bukhara, Samarkand, Termiz, Khiva and Shahrizabz located in the territory of our country, our buildings with ancient structures and unique architectural solutions are famous all over the world, people of the world dream of visiting these cities. A number of our religious shrines in Uzbekistan are directly attracting the attention of Muslim nations of the world. Our religious shrines in regions such as Al-Bukhari and At-Tirmizi have a special place in the Islamic world.

In order to organize and develop Pilgrimage tourism in our country, starting from 2018, efforts were made to attract tourists from Malaysia, Indonesia and Singapore to the holy places in Uzbekistan, a visa-free regime was introduced and additional charter flights were organized.

If we divide foreign citizens visiting Uzbekistan according to their goals, we can see that their indicators differ greatly from each other. Taking into account the potential of tourism in our country, it can be observed that there are opportunities for the development of many types of tourism.

Conclusion

In short, the organizational-methodical component of the technology of developing volitional qualities in physical education requires a reflexive point of view in future physical education teachers and creates an opportunity to develop volitional qualities based on a competency approach.

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